

Immobilisation and Release of Sulphur in Soil following Addition of Organic Materials of Varying Decomposability and Composition

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Manuscript received 25 March 1982, revised 21 July 1984, accepted 9 June 1985

Laboratory incubation studies were conducted on immobilisation and release of sulphur from native soil organic matter and added organic matter of different composition and decomposability. Mineralisation of sulphur from native soil organic matter was found to depend on its organic sulphur content and not so much on C : S ratio or available sulphate sulphur content of the soil. However, sulphur mineralising capacity of added organic matter depends on the concentration of sulphur in the added organic matter and upon the initial sulphate sulphur content of the soil. The results show the value of organic matter addition as well as its nature and source of available sulphate sulphur in soil.

A small amount of sulphate sulphur present in the soil is hardly capable of meeting the sulphur requirement of the plants grown on these soils. Hence, plants largely depend upon the conversion of soil organic sulphur to inorganic sulphate sulphur. In a recent study¹ the authors observed 74.7 to 99.7% of the total sulphur is in the organic form in non-saline surface soil of West Bengal. For the same reason, it is important to consider seriously the mineralisation and immobilisation of sulphur in different types of soils. Choi and Rossi² concluded that the addition of organic residue of plant and animal origin to soil can, with time, markedly affect the supply of plant available sulphur, and depending upon the chemical composition of organic material added to soil, inorganic sulphate sulphur may either be increased or slightly decreased. In the present investigation a laboratory experiment has, therefore, been undertaken to determine mineralisation of sulphur with time of incubation of soil, unamended and amended, with organic materials of varying decomposability and composition. Another objective of the study is to investigate the effect of sulphur content of added organic matter on its mineralisation, of which very little information is available.

Experimental

Three soils selected for this study were collected from surface layer (0-15 cm depth) of Mundabasti village of Darjeeling district in Hill region, Chinsurah of Hooghly district in Gangetic alluvial region and Sriniketan of Birbhum district in lateritic region, which, according to U.S.D.A. classification, come under palehumults, udifluvents and udalfs, respectively. Each soil was treated with three types of organic matter namely, farm yard manure, mustard seed cake and dried cowpea leaves. The organic

materials were finely ground before addition. Some relevant analytical values of the added organic materials and soil characteristics are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

For the incubation study, duplicate samples of 25 g each of the three air-dried soils, passed through 0.5 mm sieve, were taken in glass containers and each of the above three organic matters was separately added at the rate of 1% of the soil and thoroughly mixed. A similar treatment without added organic matter for each soil was also incubated as control. The soils were then moistened to 50% of their respective water holding capacities, i.e. moisture tension of 0.4, 0.33 and 0.3 atmosphere for Sriniketan, Chinsurah and Mundabasti soils, respectively and allowed to incubate at laboratory room temperature ($30 \pm 5^\circ$) for 75 days. There were five sampling stages corresponding to 15, 30, 45, 60 and 75 days after the soils were moistened. Loss of moisture due to evaporation was replenished by the addition of water on every alternate day by difference in weight. Separate sets were maintained for each sampling stage. At each sampling stage, available sulphur was extracted by 0.15% calcium chloride solution using a soil-solution ratio 1 : 2.5 (Barrow³). Sulphur content in the extract was determined by the reduction method of Johnson and Nishita⁴. The effect of the added organic materials to the soil was computed by subtracting the result of analysis for the soil not treated with organic matter, from that for the soil plus organic matter additions. The effect thus defined is the effect of the added organic matter.

Results and Discussion

Mineralisation of sulphur from native soil organic matter is not so much dependent on C : S

TABLE 1—RELEVANT CHARACTERISTICS OF SOIL USED FOR INCUBATION STUDIES

Soil collected from	pH (1:2.5)	Clay %	Organic C %	Total N %	Organic S %	Available sulphate S (ppm)	C : S	C : N : S
Mundabasti	4.9	39.5	3.14	0.424	0.0218	0.62	144.0	74 : 10 : 0.51
Chinsurah	6.0	65.2	0.77	0.071	0.0049	12.81	158.0	109 : 10 : 0.69
Sriniketan	5.8	11.8	0.23	0.024	0.0044	5.94	53.0	97 : 10 : 1.80

TABLE 2—CARBON, NITROGEN AND SULPHUR CONTENT AND THEIR PROPORTIONS IN ORGANIC MATERIALS USED

Organic matter	Organic C %	Total N %	Total S %	C : N	C : S	N : S	C : N : S
Farmyard manure	9.0	0.8	0.13	11.2	69.2	6.15	112 : 10 : 1.6
Cowpea leaves	34.8	3.2	0.37	10.8	94.0	8.64	94 : 10 : 1.5
Mustard cake	35.3	4.9	0.68	7.2	51.9	7.20	72 : 10 : 1.4

TABLE 3—IMMOBILISATION AND RELEASE OF SULPHUR IN MOIST SOILS DURING 15-75 DAYS OF INCUBATION

Soil collected from	Soil samples			S-mineralised/immobilised (ppm)				
	C : S ratio	Organic S ppm	Available sulphate S ppm	Incubation period in days				
				15	30	45	60	75
Chinsurah	158	49	12.81	2.81	-3.43	-4.37	-5.94	-5.00
Sriniketan	53	44	5.94	-2.51	-5.78	-5.78	—	-5.00
Mundabasti	144	218	0.62	5.00	1.57	2.19	2.18	2.50

ratio or available sulphate sulphur content of the soil organic matter. With low sulphur content in the soil organic matter, there was a tendency for sulphur immobilisation, whereas, mineralisation occurred in soil containing high organic sulphur (Table 3). Immobilisation of sulphate sulphur occurred in the Chinsurah soil of the alluvial tract and Sriniketan soil of the lateritic region containing low amount of sulphur in the soil organic matter (49 and 44 ppm, respectively). Whereas, mineralisation was seen in Mundabasti soil having a similar C : S ratio as in the soil of Chinsurah but containing high organic sulphur (218 ppm). Barrow^a also failed to observe any mineralisation of sulphur on incubating an unfertilised soil of native pasture, which he attributed to low sulphur content in the decomposing fraction of soil organic matter.

Results (Table 4) indicate release of available sulphate sulphur (mineralisation) in Chinsurah and Sriniketan soil following the addition of organic matter irrespective of their composition. With similar treatments and under similar incubating condition immobilisation of available sulphate sulphur was, however, noticed in Mundabasti soil. It is pertinent to indicate here that the available sulphate sulphur content of the Chinsurah and

TABLE 4 EFFECT OF ADDED ORGANIC MATTER ON IMMOBILISATION AND RELEASE OF SULPHUR IN SOILS DURING 15-75 DAYS OF INCUBATION

Incubation period days	Organic matter added	Chinsurah		Sriniketan		Mundabasti	
		A	B	A	B	A	B
15	F.Y.M.	12.19	-3.43	10.47	7.03	1.56	-4.06
	Cowpea	19.37	3.75	9.37	5.93	1.25	-4.37
	Mustard cake	67.19	51.57	44.84	41.43	1.37	-4.25
30	F.Y.M.	10.62	1.24	0.16	0	0.62	-1.57
	Cowpea	12.50	3.12	7.81	7.65	0.94	-1.25
	Mustard cake	57.31	48.43	47.81	47.65	2.50	0.31
45	F.Y.M.	15.62	7.18	0.47	0.31	0	-2.81
	Cowpea	12.19	3.75	1.25	1.09	0.87	-1.93
	Mustard cake	40.62	32.18	24.37	24.21	3.00	0.19
60	F.Y.M.	14.06	7.19	8.59	3.90	1.12	-2.32
	Cowpea	15.62	8.75	—	—	1.56	-1.88
	Mustard cake	40.94	31.07	33.44	33.75	5.75	2.31
75	F.Y.M.	12.81	5.00	6.25	5.31	0.94	-2.81
	Cowpea	—	—	4.06	3.12	1.12	-2.00
	Mustard cake	41.40	33.59	20.94	20.00	4.69	1.57

A = Available sulphate sulphur (ppm); B = Increase over control (ppm).

Sriniketan soil was higher (12.81 and 5.94 ppm, respectively) than that of the Mundabasti soil (0.62 ppm). The result, therefore, indicates that sulphur mineralising capacity of added organic matter depends upon initial sulphate sulphur content of the soil. Massoumi and Cornfield⁵ have also made a similar observation.

Irrespective of the length of incubation period and the nature of the soil used, mustard seed cake was found to be most efficient among the three added organic matters in releasing available sulphate sulphur. Dried cowpea leaf was next in order, whereas farm yard manure was found to be least efficient in releasing sulphur (Table 4). The total sulphur content of mustard seed cake, dried cowpea leaves and farm yard manure used in the present investigation were 0.68, 0.37 and 0.13%, respectively. Massoumi and Cornfield⁵ pointed out that organic materials containing sulphur in the region of 0.3% is critical for sulphur mineralisation. The present study confirms their observation.

Due to its interaction with soil organic matter, sulphur mineralisation of the added organic matter is usually overestimated. In spite of this, sulphur mineralisation was found to be closely related to sulphur content of the added organic matter. The

results thus indicate that the amount of available sulphate sulphur released or immobilised following the addition of organic matter depends on the sulphur content of added organic matter⁶. Although appreciable amounts of sulphur were not mineralised during the period of incubation fixed in this experiment, the value of organic matter addition as well as its nature as source of available sulphate sulphur in soil has been clearly demonstrated.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P.M.) is grateful to Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Fellowship.

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